

Using English Reader's Digest to Enhance Vocabulary of Pakistani Students at Tertiary Level: An Experimental Study

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 03, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Vocabulary, Reader's Digest, Spelling, Word Class, Word Usage, Language Teaching</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4734296</p>	<p><i>The present research aimed at analyzing Reader's digest to enhance vocabulary related to health, home, food, and travel of tertiary level Pakistani students. The study also designed to develop students' knowledge in the vocabulary related aspects including meaning, spelling, word class, and word usage. According to Alqahtani (2015), vocabulary plays an important role in language learning and a learner may face problems in comprehension if s/he does not possess sufficient word knowledge. The present study has focused on the formal vocabulary teaching through Reader's digest that has contributed a great deal in implementing new methods of language teaching. This mixed method research used qualitative and quantitative methods to analyze the effectiveness of Reader's digest in developing vocabulary of BS economics' students studying at a Pakistani university. The study used an experiment to analyze the effectiveness of Reader's digest using a pretest-posttest design. A closed-ended questionnaire and an interview were also used to know the responses of the participants regarding the effectiveness of Reader's digest for vocabulary enhancement. The study concludes that Reader's digest is a useful authentic material to enhance vocabulary related to health, home, food, and travel of tertiary level Pakistani students. It is also concluded that Reader's digest improves knowledge of vocabulary related aspects such as spelling, word class, and word usage, as the results of post-test demonstrate a significant improvement in students' knowledge related to these areas.</i></p>

Introduction

The present study aimed at analyzing Reader's digest to develop vocabulary of students at tertiary level in various fields, such as, health, home, food, and travel. Moreover, it devised a methodology to improve vocabulary related knowledge, including meaning, spelling, word class, and usage. According to Alqahtani (2015) and Norazmi (2020), vocabulary plays an important role in language learning and a learner may face problem in comprehension if s/he does not possess sufficient word knowledge. The present study has focused on the formal vocabulary learning through Reader's digest that has contributed a great deal in implementing new methods of language teaching. In recent years, vocabulary teaching has become an important part of teaching and learning worldwide. According to Barcroft (2004) and Norazmi et al. (2019), vocabulary has a great importance in second language learning. Researchers have found that students encounter some communication problems, as they lack sufficient stock of words.

English in Pakistan is taught as a subject across the country from grade one to ten that does not guarantee learners of English to master its different skills. It is taught as a language at small scale with ineffective teaching strategies. English is still taught as a subject and not as a language in Pakistan (Nawab, 2012; Saeed, Uzair, & Mahmood, 2012; Norazmi et al., 2020). Furthermore, the quite outdated method used in teaching vocabulary is teaching synonyms/ antonyms or making sentences of the difficult words. However, vocabulary teaching requires the incorporation of certain other skills such as teaching form of words or identifying meanings in context because this contextual usage is important for comprehension (Mazhar, Ahmed, & Aslam, 2015; Muhammad, 2013; Zaid et al., 2020). Apart from using outdated methods, over dependency on textbooks is another flaw in English language teaching as textbooks are the only available sources in Pakistan. Therefore, the traditional methods of English language teaching promote rote learning and memorization of vocabulary, which does not enable students to practically utilize the learned words in communication (Panzai & Channa, 2017; Zaedi, 2012; Zaid et al., 2021). The same situation prevails even at university level. Muhammad (2013), conducted a survey of 71 English language teachers of 6 public sector universities of Pakistan. It is revealed that the majority of English language teachers at university level still use traditional methods of teaching. Therefore, it is the need of the hour that teachers find new ways of teaching vocabulary such as newspapers, magazines and digests etc.

According to Salaberry (2001) and Rosnee et al. (2021), newspapers, magazines and digests have become a part of modern life and they have a tremendous power in molding the public opinion. They have become a powerful source of bringing reforms in the society and causing an impact on the policies of the government. These sources provide us news of various types. We read a newspaper, magazine or a digest because we have a general ability of language that helps us understand. Teaching of different skills of English language has undergone many changes in the past few decades and new ways of teaching have been experimented and successfully implemented for language teaching. One of the new ways is to use authentic material for language pedagogy that has proved to be a fruitful aid. Authentic material has been defined as “...real life texts, not written for pedagogic purposes” (Wallace, 1992, p.145). Real life texts mean that the language of everyday life is used in authentic texts. There are different resources of authentic texts including newspapers, magazines, movies, songs, literature and T V programs. Authentic material is effective for language teaching, as it contains the language that is practically used in different contexts. Widdowson (1990), also supports the use of authentic material for language teaching. He says that the language that is taught to the learners should be easy and comprehensible and this can be easily done using authentic material.

The use of authentic material provides a useful aid to a language teacher for resourceful teaching. Berardo (2006) and Fauziyana et al. (2021), endorse the idea of using additional material in a language classroom and says that authentic material enables learners to get maximum exposure to real life language and its usage. With the help of authentic material, students learn in a controlled environment of class to use language in different contexts that enables them to use accurate language. He further says that instead of providing artificial language to the learners, the teachers should find new ways to aid their teaching with authentic material. Therefore, the use of authentic material, such as, newspapers and magazines, enables learners to exercise real life language which they can easily practice in different contexts outside the classroom.

The present research aimed at teaching vocabulary through Reader’s digest to the students of BS Economics studying at one university of Pakistan. BS Economics is a four years degree program and the main course consists of the subjects related to Economics and Finance. In addition, English is taught as a compulsory course in first, second and fourth semester. Overall proficiency level of a majority of students is low in English because they are taught English as a subject and not as a language. According to Mohapatra (2014), students who have not English as their major subject struggle with English language skills. It is because, their vocabulary is not sufficient to meet their communicative needs for spoken or written purposes. They do not have sufficient word-bank to use in oral or written communication. The research, finding a gap, proposed a methodology to teach vocabulary which will be beneficial for both the teachers and the students. An experimental study was conducted to analyze the effectiveness of Reader’s digest to teach vocabulary. Reader’s digest is a world famous magazine which is read by millions of people. It is published on monthly basis and an Asian version of Reader’s digest is published every month. It is a general interest family magazine which attracts a wide readership. According to Robyns (1994), Reader’s digest is published in more than 17 languages and is the world’s bestselling magazine distributed over 162 countries worldwide. Reader’s digest was founded in the US in 1922 and its other editions were launched afterwards. Robyns (1994), says that this magazine has over 100 million readerships in the world. He also says that its research department consisting over 80 staff members verifies every fact presented in Reader’s digest.

2. Literature Review

Learning vocabulary becomes important in second language learning and it plays the central role in communication. Without vocabulary, a learner cannot communicate even if s/he has complete command on grammar and syntax (Harmar, 1991; Gough, 2001; Aminah et al., 2021). Good language teachers always pay equal attention to grammar and vocabulary (Allen, 1983; Roszi et al., 2021). Furthermore, vocabulary plays an important role in all the four skills of language including reading, writing, listening and speaking respectively. Sedita (2005), creates a strong connection between vocabulary and reading and she says that both skills are necessary and are inextricably connected. English language learners’ (ELLS) reading is directly related to their knowledge of vocabulary. The knowledge of vocabulary plays an important role in reading comprehension and readers with less vocabulary knowledge do not do well in this skill (Moghadam, Zainal, & Ghaderpour, 2012; August & Carlo, 2005; NikNurhalida et al., 2021). Similarly, vocabulary is closely associated with writing skills and cannot be neglected at the same time (Astika, 1993; Firkhan et al., 2021; Ishak et al., 2021).

Most of the times, it is supposed by some researchers that vocabulary cannot be taught in classroom and it comes naturally, therefore, Learners can acquire vocabulary and master it with passage of time, but this is not the case. Folse (2004), says that learning English as foreign language is altogether different from acquiring English language. He says that what a learner in the USA learns in a 50 minutes class of 30 weeks is a different situation and such learning experience cannot be compared to the learning attempt of a student in any other country where English is not a native language because when it is a native language a child can easily acquire it from surroundings but it is all together difficult in the case of EFL. Therefore, teachers need to adapt multiple and interesting ways such as authentic materials to make the teaching of vocabulary effective for the learners.

Azri and Rashidi (2014), state that teachers started using authentic material in 1970s after the introduction of communicative language teaching approach. Different writers have defined authentic material differently. Nunan (1999), defines authentic material as “*spoken or written material, which are not intended for use in teaching*”. Similarly, Herod (2002), argues that authentic material consists of activities which demonstrate real world language. Therefore, authentic material represents the language as it is actually used in a society. Moreover, authentic material is not specifically produced for pedagogic purposes.

To continue with the effectiveness of authentic material, it is worth mentioning that along with other language skills, vocabulary can also be effectively taught through it. Zoghi, Zardik, and Kazemi (2014), support the use of authentic material to enhance vocabulary of foreign language learners. Various researches have been carried out to analyze the effectiveness of authentic material for vocabulary development and all the researchers including Sanchez and Schmitt (2010), Zoghi, Zardik, and Kazemi (2014), Guo (2012), Saeed, Uzair, and Mahmood (2012), IsazadehandMakeri (2016), MohdNorazmi et al. (2021) and Beltran, Contesse, & Lopez (2010), support the use of authentic material to develop vocabulary of second language learners. Authentic material is a useful source and helps second language learners achieving the required vocabulary in an effective way.

While teaching vocabulary, it is not only meaning and content that are important and need to be taught. In an ESL classroom, related matters of vocabulary such as spelling and word class are also important. A second language learner is required to focus on spelling and word class along with lexical knowledge (Ehri & Rosenthal, 2007). Teaching spelling, word class, and collocation along with vocabulary makes the usage of vocabulary more effective and accurate. Researchers including Pigada and Schmitt (2006), Sanchez and Schmitt (2010), Day and Swan (1998), and Daskalovska (2011), carried out studies to analyze the effectiveness of authentic materials for vocabulary enhancement relating it to other concepts such as spelling, word class, and collocation. All of these researchers encourage language teachers to benefit from authentic materials to develop students' vocabulary and its related fields including spelling, word class, and collocation.

Vocabulary teaching has undergone many changes over the years. Shen (2003), writes that during 1980s, some researchers severely criticized the ignored importance of vocabulary because vocabulary teaching was not considered a separate skill. According to Nation (1997), it was during late 1980s, when researchers started centering vocabulary. They were able to make this stance that due to lack of vocabulary, learners face problems in receptive as well as in productive skills. Nation (1997), is also of the opinion that even advanced learners of English language feel the need for more vocabulary at some level. Therefore, it was realized that learners of English could not do well without lexical competence. Various authors have struggled to make teaching/learning of vocabulary easy and effective due to which multiple vocabulary teaching strategies have been formed.

Oxford and Crookall (as cited in Shen, 2003), put vocabulary teaching approaches into four categories. First is *de-contextualizing* using word lists, flash cards, and use of dictionary. Second is *semi-contextualizing* through word grouping, association, and semantic mapping. Third strategy is *full-contextualizing* and it includes reading, listening, speaking, and writing. Finally, fourth category is named as *adoptable*, which is based on structural reviewing. Therefore, all of the above-mentioned strategies are necessary for the teaching of vocabulary skill. The main purpose of applying any strategy definitely is to enhance learners' word bank so that they may achieve if not native like but at least near native like input of words. Brown and Payne (as cited in Shen, 2003), presented a 5R model for vocabulary development. 5R has five processes namely, *receiving*, *recognizing*, *retaining*, *retrieving*, and *recycling*. The first R is receiving, which means encountering a word. There are various ways to encounter a word. It can be done intentionally or incidentally. Learners can encounter a word in a controlled environment of class or through some other sources. Second is recognizing, that is to get the form of a word. Learners are to create a morphological image of the word they are learning. Third R is retaining, which is get a clear image of the word. Fourth step is retrieving, that is to learn the meaning of the word. Final step is recycling, which is to use the word in any context or communication.

Sripada and Cherukuri (2016), also forward some techniques for better vocabulary instruction. They propose a process of presenting vocabulary, which consists of three steps namely, *noticing*, *storing*, and *consolidating*. First step is to notice various properties of a word including morphology, phonology, syntax, stylistics, semantics, and collocation. Second step is to store the word in memory and third step further includes exploitation of a word and using it in different contexts. The question which is asked by language teachers frequently is which method of vocabulary instruction is better. Sedita (2005), has answered this question. Sedita (2005), stated that there is no one specific method which should be considered the best for vocabulary instruction. Rather, both direct and indirect methods should be used to teach vocabulary. Direct teaching means that when a teacher intends to teach specific vocabulary to students. The teacher selects some words to teach during class time and then s/he makes students read a passage. Sedita (2005), says that around 400 words can be explicitly taught to students in a year. On contrary, indirect vocabulary, instruction can be done by making students read a lot and by exposing many new words. The more students are involved in reading, the more vocabulary knowledge they will gain. So we can say that reading is directly proportional to vocabulary knowledge. For this purpose, students should read different texts at different times.

Various other strategies have been created and applied for vocabulary instruction. Anuthama (2010), discusses different methods of vocabulary teaching. First method that is discussed by him is called ‘*The Ripple Effect*’. According

to this method, words and their meanings work like a ripple, extending from center and moving outwards. This method is said to be very effective at tertiary level for vocabulary instruction. It says that majority of English words have more than one meanings and all the meanings are related to each other somehow. So a teacher can teach various meanings of word through ripple effect. For example, the word head has various meanings, which are related to each other. Even abstract ideas can be taught through this method. One of the major benefits of this method is that students learn to make associations by using their imagination to discover more related words. The teacher has to just activate students' imagination and the process of learning words starts.

Second method that is discussed is 'Teaching vocabulary in colors'. A teacher of English Gnoinska in Poland developed this method. Anuthama (2010), says that this method uses colors for vocabulary instruction. Different colors attract the attention of human beings and they have a huge impact over health and psychology. In this method, different colors are used for better understanding and comprehension of meaning, pronunciation, and spelling. Colored chalks, pencils, and markers can be used for this purpose. This method is also very interesting for students as it is very easy to remember something like a text, which is highlighted in different colors than a simple and clean text. To sum up, various strategies have been introduced by different researchers and language experts for effective vocabulary instruction and all strategies may prove effective depending on situation and learning needs of the students. The success of any strategy also depends on the educational context where it is applied and experimented. 5 R model may or may not prove to be effective in a specific learning context. Similarly, three Rs, the ripple effect, and color method, have variation in use and application depending upon learners and their language needs.

The previous studies mentioned in this chapter focused vocabulary teaching without linking it to any field, however, the present study fills this gap by relating vocabulary instruction with the fields of health, home, food, and travel. The present research is related to vocabulary development through reader's digest, which is a written authentic material. The research links vocabulary with spelling, word class, and meaning usage. Though several studies have been conducted on vocabulary development through authentic material, this study is different in its nature because it investigates the effectiveness of an authentic magazine to develop vocabulary of tertiary level students specially focusing the fields of health, home, food, and travel, which sets a new dimension for other researchers and language teachers. Finally, the sample of this study also makes it distinct, as the participants were students of BS economics and finance, who do not study English as a major subject. Therefore, the researcher has put his efforts to explore a different aspect of vocabulary development using an authentic magazine which may further set a new dimension for other researchers to explore the related issues.

3. Research Methodology

This mixed method research used qualitative and quantitative methods to analyze the effectiveness of Reader's digest in developing vocabulary of BS economics' students studying at a university. The study used an experiment to analyze the effectiveness of Reader's digest. The present study was a single group experimental research, which follows a pre-test and a post-test for the collection of main data. The present research used single group experimental design because it was the most appropriate design to analyze the effectiveness of Reader's digest to develop vocabulary of BS economics students. The reason of selecting this design was that the effectiveness of independent variable could only be analyzed involving all students in form of one group. Students of BS economics study business English without special focus on different language skills. Therefore, effect of Reader's digest on students' vocabulary was tested without dividing them into two groups.

This study was guided by the methodology, which is used by Sanchez and Schmitt (2010). They conducted a study to analyze the effectiveness of an authentic novel, *Things Fall Apart*, to test meaning knowledge, spelling, and word class. The participants were 20 Spanish learners of English language who studied in England for one year. Out of 20 participants, 12 were males and eight were females. The researchers selected 34 African words, which were used in the novel. Thirty out of thirty four words were nouns and rest of four words could be used as nouns or adjectives. The words were selected based on their frequency of occurrence in the novel. The present study aimed at vocabulary development through Reader's digest, which is an authentic magazine. The study involved practical classroom teaching. To conduct the study, fifty participants were involved who were studying in BS Economics and Finance course in one university of Pakistan. The students of BS Economics first, second and fourth semesters made the sample of this study as all of these semesters had English as a compulsory subject. Students in these three semesters were fifty as this is the average strength of the students in three classes. Minimum age of these students is 18 years and maximum age is around 22. These students come from different provinces of Pakistan. The students at this level study English as a compulsory subject, which includes various contents including business English, communication skills, reading and writing skills. Students at this level face problems regarding the use of words, as their word-bank is not sufficient to fulfill their needs.

The present study adapted the model mentioned above with some slight changes. The present study involved classroom teaching and was analyzed based on participants' performance. Field oriented vocabulary was focused in the classroom teaching that included health, food, home and travel. Fifty participants were involved who were studying in BS Economics and Finance. An authentic magazine, Reader's digest was selected as the source to enhance knowledge of the participant regarding meaning, spelling, word class and word usage. The instruments included pre-test, post-test, questionnaire, and interviews. The participants were briefed about the whole process of using Reader's digest. A pre-test

was conducted initially testing students' knowledge of meaning, spelling, word class and word usage. Pre-test and post-test had four questions to test the knowledge of the participants in the areas of spelling, meaning knowledge, word class, and meaning usage. In the first question, the participants were tested in spellings and for this purpose; the researcher dictated ten difficult words in the passage to the participants. After this activity, the researcher collected the answer sheets from the participants and passed the remaining test to further check vocabulary through ten multiple-choice questions in which the participants were instructed to solve the activities to test meaning knowledge. In third question, the participants were instructed to write the part of speech of the underlined word in ten sentences. In the fourth question, the participants were instructed to write a paragraph to check the practical application of ten words in a specific field with which the words belong. Each section of pre-test contained ten marks making a total of forty.

Pre-test was followed by teaching phase where students were made to read texts from Reader's digest. The participants were taught twenty-four passages from Reader's digest related to health, food, home and travel with six passages each focusing on the knowledge of meaning, spelling, word class, and meaning usage. After teaching phase, a post-test was conducted on the pattern of pre-test. The scores of pre-test and post-test were compared and analyzed statistically displaying percentages for meaning knowledge, spelling, word class, and word usage. Later, all the participants filled a closed-ended questionnaire to give their feedback on the utility of Reader's digest. Finally, 10 students were interviewed. They answered an open-ended questionnaire to further provide their ideas regarding the use of Reader's digest for vocabulary development. Only those ten students were interviewed who showed significant improvement in post-test. The numeric data gathered through pre-test and post-test were statistically analyzed. Similarly, questions of questionnaire were also statistically analyzed using SPSS. Finally, interviews were qualitatively analyzed using NVIVO.

4. Results

The present study aimed to analyze the effectiveness of Reader's digest to develop the vocabulary of students in the areas of health, home, food, and travel. The study also aimed to enable the participants to practically utilize the knowledge of meaning, spelling, and word class. The data for this study were analyzed in three stages. In the first stage, data gathered through pre-test and post-test were analyzed. In the second stage, the analysis of questionnaire has been presented, whereas, interviews were analyzed qualitatively. The results of pre-test and post-test were analyzed statistically through SPSS using paired sample t-test as the same group of the participants was involved before and after the experiment. The results of paired sample t-test are presented below.

Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Total Score Pre.	11.00	50	4.209	0.595
	& Post-test	27.62	50	4.476	0.633

The above table demonstrates the results of pre-test and post-test in comparison as it displays the mean value for both the tests. As shown in the above table, the mean value for the pre-test was 11 which increased to 27.62 in the post-test. The improvement in the mean value indicates significant improvement in the knowledge of vocabulary of the participants. Pre-test was followed by the teaching stage where the participants were taught vocabulary and its related aspects through Reader's digest. The participants showed a significant improvement in the knowledge of vocabulary and its related aspects such as spelling, word class, and word usage.

Paired Samples Correlations

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Total Score Pre. & Post-test	50	0.742	.000

The above table displays the correlation and significance level between the scores of pre-test and post-test for the same sample of 50 students. The correlation demonstrated is 0.74 which indicates linear dependence between pre-test and post-test. The value of the correlation coefficient (0.74) indicates that the exploitation of independent variable broke exact linear relationship into linear relationship. Had there been no experiment, correlation coefficient would have been equal to exact one.

Paired Sample test

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Total Score Pre. & Post-test	-16.620	3.129	.443	-17.509	-15.731	-37.557	49	.000

The above results demonstrate that the participants had a low mean of eleven in the pre-test, which increased to 27.62 in the post-test showing a significant improvement in the knowledge of vocabulary. The results display the mean as -16.620, which indicates a significant improvement in students' knowledge of vocabulary. Likewise, the above table displays the significance level that is less than .05, therefore, the difference in students' knowledge of vocabulary is significant. Furthermore, the confidence interval level displayed in the results is 95%, which indicates that there will be a significant difference between the scores of pre-test and post-test whenever such a test is conducted. Therefore, the above results demonstrate a significant improvement in students' vocabulary knowledge which is enhanced through Reader's digest.

The participants of this study were given a questionnaire to know their responses regarding the utility of Reader's digest for vocabulary enhancement. Nearly all the participants laid their confidence on the utility of Reader's digest for vocabulary enhancement. They were of the view that Reader's digest is interesting and informative and it focus on various age groups as it has variety of topics which further improves readers' cultural awareness about various societies . The participants also said that the language of Reader's digest is a little advanced and the have to consult dictionary sometimes. They found the language of the digest challenging. Moreover, the respondents consider Reader's digest to be a useful source to enhance vocabulary at tertiary level in various fields including health, home, food, and travel. The respondents believe Reader's digest to be extremely effective for vocabulary enhancement to a great extent as they showed a significant improvement in post-test results. Similarly, the participants consider Reader's digest to an effective source to improve the knowledge of spelling and word class which further helps to use the words more appropriately. They were also of the opinion that knowledge of meaning, spelling, and word class further enables them to improve their writing skills. The participants also agreed that vocabulary learned through Reader's digest further helps to communicate in varied contexts as it provides sufficient word knowledge related to various fields.

The participants were of the opinion that Reader's digest in classroom provides them autonomy to benefit from it in future without any mentoring. Having been taught through Reader's digest, the participants agreed that all language teachers should use Reader's digest in their classes to improve students' knowledge of vocabulary and other language skills such as writing, reading, and speaking. In the end, the respondents agreed that Reader's digest may also be a useful source for vocabulary teaching in various other courses such as BBA, MBA, IT, and Engineering. The participants of this study agreed that Reader's digest is an effective source to improve vocabulary of tertiary level students in the fields of health, home, food, and travel.

Interviews of those participants were conducted who showed significant improvement in post-test then the others. Ten participants were interviewed so that more elaborated responses could be known. A semi-structured interview was designed which consisted of five questions. A qualitative data analysis tool, NVIVO, was used to analyze the interviews. The analysis of the questions is as follows.

Q 1 Which methods have you been exposed to learn vocabulary so far? How do you compare those with the recent methods you have experienced?

Q 2 How far was Reader's digest helpful in enhancing your word bank related to different fields including home, health, food, and travel?

Q 3 How will Reader's digest help you fulfill your communicative needs?

Q 4 Do you think that teachers should use Reader’s digest to enhance vocabulary of students at various other levels including BBA, MBA, IT, and engineering? Why?

Q 5 What further suggestions would you have regarding the use of helping material such as Reader’s digest to improve word bank of students?

Initially, the participants were inquired about their way of learning vocabulary before the use of Reader's digest. All the respondents were of the view that the methodology they had been using before to learn vocabulary was not effective as the previous methodology favored memorization of the words with their meanings making it boring and ineffective. On the other hand, they believe Reader's digest to be effective for vocabulary development as they do not have to memorize words rather they learn the words along with their usage. The participants consider learning vocabulary through Reader's digest to be motivating and interesting. In other words, they negate the previous methods of learning vocabulary which they consider boring and ineffective. The respondents transcribed their responses and were of the opinion that Reader's digest enhances vocabulary related to various fields including health, home, food, and travel to a great extent.

When the participants were questioned about the utility of Reader's digest, they were of the opinion that it will help them to improve their reading, writing, and speaking skills as improved vocabulary. Furthermore, the participants favored using Reader's digest in other courses including BBA, MBA, IT, and Engineering as it is an effective source to enhance vocabulary. In the end, the participants suggested the regular and extended use of Reader's digest. They were of the opinion that if Reader's digest is regularly, the students will continuously benefit from it. Moreover, they suggested the extended use of Reader's digest expanding it to various other fields as the present study was delimited to the fields of health, home, food, and travel.

5. Findings

Based on the data analysis, it is found that Reader's digest improves vocabulary of tertiary level students significantly. It is also demonstrated that Reader's digest improves vocabulary of the students in an interesting and productive way as they do not find it boring. It not only enhances vocabulary but also helps students to practically apply the knowledge of vocabulary for the improvement of other skills such as reading, writing, and speaking. Through the analysis of data, it is displayed that the participants of this study consider Reader's digest as a valuable source to enhance word knowledge related to various fields such as health, home, food, and travel. The Participants of this study suggested the regular use of Reader's digest at various other courses where English is not taught as a major subject. Similarly, they suggested English language teachers to use Reader's digest in their classes to increase vocabulary of their students.

6. Conclusion

Through the findings, the study concludes that Reader's digest is a useful source to enhance vocabulary of tertiary level Pakistani students in the fields of health, home, food, and travel. It is also concluded that Reader's digest improves knowledge of vocabulary related areas such as spelling, word class, and word usage, as the results of post-test demonstrate a significant improvement in students' knowledge related to these areas. Reader's digest enables students to practically apply the learned knowledge of vocabulary in their day to day communication in writing and speaking. It is further demonstrated that unlike traditional methods of vocabulary teaching, Reader's digest improves vocabulary of the students in an interesting and innovative way. The study concludes that improved vocabulary through Reader's digest further helps students to develop other language

skills such as reading, writing, and speaking. To sum up, Reader's digest is a useful authentic material to enhance vocabulary of tertiary level students in the fields of health, home, food, and travel.

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